

Przewalskinone-B from the Stem Bark of *Ochna obtusata*

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O. obtusata Kanis. (Syn : *O. jabotapita* Linn. and *O. squarrosa* Linn.; Fam : Ochnaceae) is a small tree found in Assam, Bihar and the Deccan peninsula of India. The plant and its various parts are reported in indigenous systems of medicine¹. This prompted us to undertake the work.

The occurrence of n-octacosanol, sterols², flavonoids and tannins³ were reported from this plant earlier. Here we report the isolation of the anthraquinone, przewalskinone-B (1) from its stem bark which was previously isolated from *Salvia przewalskii* Maxim. of Labiatae⁴.

Shade-dried and powdered stem bark of *O. obtusata* (2.7 kg) collected from Kodikkarai forest (about 400 km south of Madras) was defatted with petroleum ether and extracted with chloroform in the cold (72 h). The chloroform extract (ca 10 g) was column chromatographed over silica gel (60–120 mesh) and eluted with solvents of increasing polarity.

Elution of the column with petroleum ether : benzene (1 : 1) gave a reddish mass which on purification by rechromatography afforded an orange compound, crystallised from acetone (m.p. 202–04°), answered anthraquinone colour test and gave elemental analysis, ir, uv, ¹H nmr and MS data corresponding to przewalskinone-

B. The structural assignment was further supported by the ¹³C nmr data : δ (100 MHz, CDCl₃) 162.6 (C-1), 124.4 (C-2), 148.5 (C-3), 121.2 (C-4), 133.5 (C-4a), 110.4 (C-10a), 165.4 (C-5), 108.2 (C-6), 166.7 (C-7), 106.9 (C-8), 135.4 (C-8a), 113.9 (C-9a), 190.9 (C-9), 181.9 (C-10), 22.1 (CH₃), 56.0 (OCH₃). This is the second report on the occurrence of this anthraquinone from a natural source and first from the family Ochnaceae.

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References

1. S. K. JAIN and C. R. TARAFDER, *Econ. Bot.*, 1970, **24**, 241; R. N. CHOPRA, S. L. NAYAR and I. C. CHOPRA, "Glossary of Indian Medicinal plants", C.S.I.R., New Delhi, 1956, p. 178.
2. K. K. PURUSHOTHAMAN, A. SARADA and M. BALAKRISHNAN, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1980, **57**, 1140; D. H. GAWAD, T. R. GOVINDACHARI, B. S. JOSHI, V. N. KAMAT, P. C. PARTHASARATHY, K. S. RAMACHANDRAN, M. N. SHANBAG, A. R. SIDHYA and N. VISWANATHAN, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1975, **13**, 97.
3. M. OKIGAWA, N. KAWANO, M. AQIL and W. RAHMAN, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1973, **22**, 2003; *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 1*, 1976, 580; A. G. R. NAIR, P. RAMESH and S. S. SUBRAMANIAN, *Curr. Sci.*, 1975, **44**, 551; F. MOHAMMED, H. M. TAUFEEQ, M. ILYAS, W. RAHMAN and J. CHOPIN, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1982, **21**, 167; K. C. REDDY, K. A. KUMAR and G. SRIMANNARAYANA, *Phytochemistry*, 1983, **22**, 800; H. O. SAXENA, *Lloydia*, 1975, **38**, 346.
4. X. Z. Lu, W. H. XU and H. NAOKI, *Phytochemistry*, 1992, **31**, 708.